

Chemical modifications of lac. Part-II. Application of some modified lac on jute fibre to improve its serviceability

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Some modified lac, such as dewaxed shellac, lac-glycol ether, lac-glycol fatty acid complex and glycol-ester of hydrolyzed lac are prepared. Effects of these products on some physical properties of jute fibre (both mordanted and unmordanted) have been studied. It is observed that the tensile strength, tenacity and moisture regain properties of the treated fibre decrease and percent elongation increases in comparison with the raw jute (control). The nature of the shades developed on jute fibre by the application of various modified lac is also reported.

Shellac is mainly a polyester condensation product of several polyhydroxy and polybasic acids and may be compared among synthetic resin to glyptals. We reported earlier¹ an exhaustive study to improve or modify the properties of shellac and shellac acids by combination with polyhydric alcohols. Several modified forms possessing improved gloss, adhesion, elasticity and water resistance were obtained. According to the nature and position of the hydroxyl and carboxylic acid groups introduced products of varying hardness from sticky balsam to a hard material can be obtained. The sticky or balsam like products may be used as varnish, plasticizers or adhesives and the harder ones, with and without fillers, as moulding resins. A modified form of shellac, obtained by reaction of OH groups of shellac and glycol to give ethylene glycol ethers, has good electrical properties, aging characteristics, flexibility and durability and can be applied to jute fabric².

Callow³ attempted to check decoloration of jute by treating it with urea-formaldehyde resin. Other workers⁴ used urea-formaldehyde and melamine-formaldehyde resins using organic as well as aqueous solvents and various catalysts. The net results were a decrease in tensile strength and rot proof on one hand and increase in wrinkle recovery and to some extent wet strength of the treated jute fibre on the other. The effect of urea-formaldehyde and melamine-formaldehyde resin precondensates on jute fibre and jute fabrics were studied in detail by Amin *et al.*⁵. They treated bleached jute fibre and fabrics with the aforesaid precondensates and studied the effects of resin as well as catalyst concentration, time and temperature of resin curing. The treated fabrics

showed marked improvement in various physical properties.

In the present investigation we have treated jute fibre with some modified lac products, viz. dewaxed shellac, lac-glycol ether, lac-glycol fatty acid complex, glycol-ester of hydrolyzed lac to bring forth new textile properties and to extend newer uses of jute.

Results and Discussion

The treated jute fibre showed marked changes in various physical and mechanical properties, such as reduction in tensile strength, reduction in moisture regain, increase in weight etc. The process appears to be a simple chemical finishing one for internal deposition of different lac products within jute fibre which modifies the textile properties of jute.

The increase in percent elongation of the treated fibre is due to the increase in cell wall thickness of the treated fibre. The percent moisture regain character of each treated jute fibre is lower than that of control (untreated). The weight gain of the fibre is due to the deposition of lac products on the fibre. A maximum of 12.73% weight gain was achieved. The variation in absorption of water vapour (moisture regain) decreases with the increase of lac-resin deposition because the latter brings forth hydrophobic characteristics in jute fibre.

The shrinkage causes loss in fibre length and it is found to be nil in the present investigation. The different shades developed on jute fibre are shown in Table 1.

The treatment causes embrittlement of the fibre and also

Note

Table 1 Effect of modified lac products on jute fibre

Sample	Colour produced	Tensile strength kg/yarn	Tenacity* g/D	Elongation %	Moisture regain %	Weight gain %	Shrinkage %
Dewaxed shellac							
Control (Untreated)	Golden	40.5	2.25	2.5	11.57	–	Nil
RJ	L. violet	34.5	1.91	8.5	7.61	6.68	Nil
RJA	L. violet	32.4	1.80	5.5	10.33	5.80	Nil
RJCu	L. violet	32.6	1.81	8.0	5.71	10.23	Nil
RJFe	Brown	22.5	1.25	5.2	8.01	9.25	Nil
RJCr	Brown	15.0	0.85	5.0	7.75	9.77	Nil
RJNi	Golden	21.5	1.19	6.0	5.39	13.41	Nil
Lac-glycol ether							
Control (Untreated)	Golden	40.5	2.25	2.5	11.57	–	Nil
RJ	Yellow	34.2	1.90	8.5	9.67	7.0	Nil
RJA	Yellow	28.0	1.55	5.8	10.10	5.5	Nil
RJCu	Brown	28.8	1.60	5.8	7.06	4.5	Nil
RJFe	Brown	24.5	1.36	5.0	8.92	8.0	Nil
RJCr	Orange	18.0	1.00	5.8	6.58	11.5	Nil
RJNi	G. yellow	27.0	1.50	5.7	6.66	12.73	Nil
Lac-glycol fatty acid complex							
Control (Untreated)	Golden	40.5	2.25	2.5	11.57	–	Nil
RJ	Brown	24.0	1.33	6.0	9.20	6.68	Nil
RJA	Yellow	25.5	1.41	6.0	9.89	7.70	Nil
RJCu	Brown	22.5	1.25	5.9	5.40	8.25	Nil
RJFe	Yellow	21.0	1.16	5.5	7.43	9.25	Nil
RJCr	Brown	24.0	1.33	6.0	6.47	3.66	Nil
RJNi	Yellow	26.0	1.44	6.4	5.31	12.12	Nil
Glycol-ester of hydrolyzed lac							
Control (Untreated)	Golden	40.5	2.25	2.5	11.57	–	Nil
RJ	L. violet	31.5	1.75	6.0	7.85	4.8	Nil
RJA	L. violet	30.0	1.66	5.5	10.34	6.6	Nil
RJCu	Violet	30.0	1.66	5.5	6.36	4.39	Nil
RJFe	Brown	28.0	1.55	5.0	7.79	8.0	Nil
RJCr	Brown	27.0	1.50	6.6	7.28	11.79	Nil
RJNi	Yellow	29.0	1.61	6.0	6.72	12.0	Nil

*D = Dimer

leads to loss of tensile strength. However, properties in the 6–8% range of resin add-on, may be a reasonable compromise between loss and improvement of properties⁶. Furthermore, the resin add-on with the fibre may be varied from this level of incorporation of resin depending upon the end-uses of jute.

Experimental

The tensile strength, percentage elongation, moisture, tenacity and percentage shrinkage were measured by standard methods⁷.

*Dewaxed shellac*¹ : The semi-powdered seed lac (1 kg)

kept in rectified spirit (4 dm³) overnight at room temperature with occasional shaking. The lac solution thus obtained was filtered and the filtrate distilled on a water-bath to recover the solvent as far as possible (85% recovery). The residue was heated on a hot-plate at 110° and the molten mass was cooled at 50° when it turned into flakes (90%).

*Lac-glycol ether*¹ : A mixture of dewaxed shellac (500 g) and ethylene glycol (187 ml) was heated in an oil-bath at 120° until all the lac dissolved. The temperature was then allowed to fall to 80° and concentrated H₂SO₄ (1.8 ml) added. The mixture was then refluxed at 180–190° for 4 h and then poured in water. The excess glycol and acid was then washed out with boiling water and the product dried by heating under vacuum over boiling water-bath. The etherified product thus obtained (70%) was soluble in most of the common solvents.

*Lac-glycol fatty acid complex*¹ : The prepared lac-glycol compound (100 g) was heated on an oil-bath at 200–205° for 30 min to remove any uncombined glycol. Double-boiled linseed oil (100 g) was then added and the esterification was carried out by heating it for 4–5 h at 150–200°. The lac-glycol fatty acid complex thus obtained (65%) was soluble in castor oil, xylene, *m*-cresol.

*Glycol-ester of hydrolyzed lac*¹ : A mixture of lac acids (250 g) and ethylene glycol (100 ml) was refluxed 24 h in an oil-bath at 195–200°, when practically a neutral product was obtained. The ester was then washed free from glycol or any other water-soluble matter by washing with boiling water and dried. The product was a dark-red sticky balsam (75%), soluble in castor oil, xylene, *m*-cresol.

Collection of jute fibre : Jute fibre (*Corchorus olitorius*, Tossa) collected from Rajshahi Jute Mills, Rajshahi, was cut off from both top and bottom ends of fibre and its middle part was separated and used. It was cleaned, dried, cut into pieces (25 cm in length) and was divided into bundles of 0.5 g; each bundle constituted a yarn for the subsequent experiments.

*Mordanting of raw jute (RJ) with copper sulfate*⁸ : A 6% mordanting bath was prepared with aqueous copper

sulfate solution. 10 yarns (5 g) of jute fibre (RJ) was introduced into the bath, heated to boiling for 30 min and then cooled. The jute fibre was then taken out, washed with distilled water and dried at room temperature (25 ± 2°). Let this mordanted raw jute sample be called RJC_u; similarly, mordanting with ferrous sulfate, chromium sulfate and nickel sulfate are called RJF_e, RJC_r and RJN_i, respectively.

Treatment of different forms of jute fibre with dewaxed shellac and other modified forms of shellac : Each of 5 yarns (2.5 g) of the experimental sample of RJ, RJA, RJC_u, RJC_r and RJN_i were immersed into an alcoholic solution of dewaxed shellac (20%) separately. After 24 h, the samples were taken out and squeezed off. The impregnated fibres were then successively washed with dilute soap solution (0.25%) and water, and dried at 105°. The physical properties of the fibre were then determined. Similar operations on the experimental yarns were carried out using other modified products of lac, viz. lac-glycol ether, lac-glycol fatty acid complex and glycol-ester of hydrolyzed lac.

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